

Folklore as a Pedagogical Resource: Teaching Values through Folksongs and Folktales

Paper ID: 21315 | Submission Date: 2026-03-11 | Acceptance Date: 2026-03-22 | Publication Date: 2026-03-25

This is an open-access research article distributed under the terms of the **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License**, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are properly credited.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19778296

For verification of this paper, please visit:
<http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Pema Yanchen
Assistant Professor
Education
Dorjee Khandu Govt.
College
Tawang, Arunachal
Pradesh, India

Abstract

This study explores folklore as a rich pedagogical resource by examining the moral and cultural values embedded in selected folktales and folksongs from Tawang District, Arunachal Pradesh. Using a qualitative approach, three traditional folksongs and five folktales from Monpa Community were analysed to identify recurring values and themes. The study further investigates how these narratives can be used as effective tools for value education in school settings. Findings reveal that Tawang's folklore reflects values such as respect, kindness, honesty, living harmoniously, hard work, resilience, cooperation, courage, the power of karma and community bonding. The study highlights the pedagogical relevance of oral traditions and suggests classroom strategies such as storytelling, discussion, role-play, music-based learning and reflective activities. The result emphasizes the importance of preserving folklore into modern teaching practices to make value education more meaningful and culturally rooted.

Keywords

Folklore, Monpa Community, Arunachal Pradesh, Pedagogy, Resource, Value Education.

Introduction

Folklore plays a vital role in preserving the cultural heritage and collective wisdom of communities. In regions like Tawang District of Arunachal Pradesh, where oral traditions remain an important part of daily life, folktales and folksongs serve as powerful carriers of values, beliefs and social norms. The Monpa community known for its vibrant traditions, has passed down stories and songs for generations, shaping the moral outlook of children and adults alike. Today, as education seeks culturally relevant and value-based approaches, these traditional narratives have the potential to enrich classroom teaching. This study examines the moral and cultural values embedded in selected folklore from Tawang and explores how such narratives can be used as pedagogical tools for value education.

Folklore serves as a powerful medium for transmitting moral, cultural, and social values across generations (Dundes, 1980). Through folktales and folksongs, essential values such as honesty, respect, cooperation, and cultural identity can be communicated in an engaging and meaningful manner. In the contemporary context, where younger generations are gradually losing connection with their cultural roots, including language and traditional practices, the role of folklore becomes even more significant (UNESCO, 2003).

From a pedagogical perspective, the integration of folklore into classroom teaching provides a culturally responsive approach to education, making learning more relatable and experiential for students. It not only enhances students' engagement and interest but also facilitates value-based education by connecting abstract concepts with lived cultural experiences. Therefore, incorporating folklore into school curriculum can act as an effective pedagogical tool to preserve cultural heritage while fostering moral development and holistic learning among students, ensuring the continuity of traditions for future generations.

Objective of study

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine teachers' familiarity with folktales and folksongs of Monpa community of Tawang.
2. To identify the moral values conveyed through folktales and folksongs.
3. To assess teachers' perceptions regarding the effectiveness of folklore in teaching values to students.
4. To find out the extent to which folklore is used in classroom teaching practices.
5. To identify the subjects in which folklore can be effectively integrated.

6. To examine teachers' perception regarding inclusion of folklore in the school curriculum
7. To examine the methods of integrating folktales and folksongs into education.
8. To analyze the perceived benefits of using folklore as pedagogical tool in classroom.
9. To identify the challenges faced by teachers in using folklore as a pedagogical tool in the classroom.

Research Questions

1. Are teachers familiar with the folktales and folksongs of Tawang/Monpa community?
2. What moral values do teachers perceive in folktales?
3. Do teachers consider folklore effective in teaching values to students?
4. To what extent do teachers use folktales and folksongs in classroom teachings?
5. In which subjects can folklore be effectively integrated?
6. Do teachers' support the inclusion of folklore in the school curriculum?
7. How can folklore and folksongs be incorporated into value education?
8. What benefits do teachers perceive in using folklore in classroom teaching?
9. What challenges do teachers face when using folklore as a teaching tool?

Review of Literature

Recent studies highlight the growing importance of folklore as a tool for cultural preservation identity formation, and value education.

1. Research by Nata and Sembiring (2020) identified several character values embedded in folklore narratives, such as kindness, courage, cooperation, and respect for others.
2. Likewise Nanda et al. (2021) found that traditional folklore such as the story of Timun Mas contains significant moral values including honesty, bravery, responsibility, and perseverance that contribute to character building among learners.
3. Similarly, Sipahutar et al. (2021) examined Batakese folklore and concluded that folktales play an important role in promoting ethical behavior and social responsibility in children.
4. Folklore has been recognized as an important pedagogical resource in educational settings. Rohmat (2023) notes that storytelling based on traditional folklore can improve children's language skills while simultaneously instilling moral and cultural values.
5. Scholars have also found the role of folklore in supporting character education. Kusuma and Nurzaman (2024) argue that folktales help develop empathy, tolerance, and moral understanding, making them valuable tools for moral and psychological development.
6. In addition, Farhin and Pratama (2025) highlight that integrating folklore into classroom teaching helps students connect with cultural heritage while strengthening character education.

These studies collectively demonstrate that folklore serves not only as a cultural expression but also as a powerful educational tool for promoting moral development, cultural awareness, and value-based learning. This supports the current study's focus on using folktales and folksongs as pedagogical tools for teaching values, particularly in culturally rich region like Tawang.

Rationale of the study:

In the present era of rapid modernization, there is a noticeable decline in the transmission of indigenous cultural knowledge among younger generations. Folklore which is traditionally served as an important medium for imparting moral and social values is gradually losing its place in formal education. This creates a need to explore relevance within contemporary pedagogical practices. Integrating folktales and folksongs into classroom teaching can promote value education while preserving cultural heritage. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the role of folklore as an effective pedagogical tool, particularly in context of Tawang / Monpa community.

Methodology

Selection of Folktales and Folk songs

The folktales and folksongs selected for the present study were drawn from the oral traditions of Monpa community of Tawang district. These narratives and songs have been passed down through generations and reflect the community's cultural heritage, beliefs, and social values. The selected folktales primarily convey moral lessons such as honesty, courage, respect for elders and harmony with nature, while the folk songs express themes of unity, tradition, and everyday life experiences. These materials were chosen based on their relevance to value education and fostering cultural awareness and moral development among students.

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive qualitative research design. This design was chosen because the objective was to understand teacher's opinions, experiences, and perceptions regarding the use of folktales and folksongs as pedagogical tools. The study selected five traditional Monpa folktales and three folksongs for analysis. These narratives were chosen based on their moral content, cultural relevance and popularity within the community. The selected texts were examined to identify embedded moral and cultural values.

Area of the study

The study was conducted in Tawang district, an area rich in oral traditions, monastic songs, and indigenous folktales. Because folklore remains an active part of cultural life in Tawang, the district was considered ideal for exploring its pedagogical relevance.

Sample and sampling technique

The sample consists of 30 teachers (English, Hindi, History and Bhoti language) from different government schools in Tawang district. Purposive sampling was used as language teachers frequently engage with storytelling, songs, cultural text and hence are the most suitable group to comment on the educational value of folklore.

Tool for data collection

A questionnaire consisting of close-ended and open-ended 12 items addressing teachers' perception, confidence, and challenges using folklore. And the data collected were analysed using descriptive, quantitative (frequency and percentage) and qualitative thematic analysis.

The findings of the study reveal a strong consensus among teachers regarding the educational and cultural value of folklore. The majority of respondents expressed that folklore is most suitable for language and social science subjects and identified interactive methods such as storytelling, role play, singing, and drama as effective strategies for classroom integration. Teachers also highlighted that folklore promotes moral values such as honesty, respect, cooperation, unity and kindness. The findings reinforce the idea that folklore is not merely a cultural artifact but an active pedagogical tool that support value-based education.

Teachers further emphasized the importance of including folklore in the school curriculum to preserve local culture, strength cultural identity, and transmit knowledge to younger generations. In the context of tribal regions like Tawang district, folklore serves as a bridge between tradition and modern education, ensuring that students remain connected to their cultural roots while engaging with formal school.

Interestingly, the findings also reflect a need for institutional support. Although teachers show willingness to use folklore, challenges such as curriculum pressure, lack of time, limited resources and insufficient training restrict its effective implementation. This indicates that policy-level and institutional initiatives are necessary to facilitate the structured integration of folklore into school education.

Historically, schools had a dedicated subject known as Moral Science, where many stories-often drawn from folklore and traditional narratives-were used to impart ethical values and life lessons. These stories played a significant role in shaping students' character, teaching empathy, honesty, discipline and respect. Overtime, with increasing academic competition and syllabus expansion, such value-oriented subjects have gradually diminished in prominence. However, the findings of this study suggest that there is a renewed need to revive value-based components within school curricula. Reintroducing structured value education possibly through folklore-based modules can support and nature young, developing minds in holistic manner.

The findings of the present study strongly align with the vision of National Education Policy 2020, which emphasizes the promotion of Indian knowledge systems, local traditions, and mother tongue/local languages as the medium of instruction, especially at foundational levels. NEP 2020 advocates for culturally responsive pedagogy and encourages the integration of local context, culture and traditions into the curriculum to make learning more meaningful and rooted.

The teachers' strong support for including folklore in the curriculum reflects this national policy direction. Folklore, being deeply embedded in local language and cultural practices, naturally supports NEP 2020's emphasis on experiential learning, holistic development, and value-based education. By incorporating folklore into classroom teaching, schools can contribute to preserving indigenous knowledge systems while fostering moral and ethical awareness among students.

Result and Discussion

Findings

Objective1: To examine teachers’ familiarity with folktales and folksongs of Monpa community of Tawang.

Research Question: Are teachers familiar with the folktales and folksongs of Tawang/Monpa community?

The responses of the teachers to the questionnaire are presented in the following tables.

Table 1: Familiarity with Local Folklore

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	28	86.7%
No	02	13.3%
Total	30	100%

Majority (86.7%) of the teachers revealed that they are familiar with local folktales and folk songs of Monpa community, which indicated a strong cultural awareness among teachers.

Objective 2: To identify the moral values conveyed through folktales and folksongs.

Research question: What moral values do teachers perceive in folktales and folksongs?

Table 2: Moral values taught by folklore

Themes identified	Frequency	Percentage
Honesty	29	93.3%
Respect for others	30	100%
Cooperation	30	100%
Unity	28	86.7%
Kindness	30	100%

“Note: Multiple responses were allowed; therefore, total frequency exceeds the number of respondents (N=30). Percentages are calculated based on the total number of respondents”

The findings shows that respect cooperation, and kindness (100%) were identified by all teachers as key moral values embedded in folklore. Honesty (93.3%) and unity (86.7%) were also strongly emphasized. This demonstrates that folklore is widely perceived as an effective medium for value education and character development. The high frequency of responses reflects a strong consensus among teachers regarding the moral richness of traditional narratives.

Objective 3: To assess teachers’ perceptions regarding the effectiveness of folklore in teaching values to students

Research question: Do teachers consider folklore effective in teaching values to students?

Table 3: Folktales effectiveness in teaching values

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	30	100%
No	00	00
Total	15	100%

All (100%) teachers revealed that folktales and folksongs are effective tool for imparting values to children. they believe that the combination of imagination and reality in folklore contributes significantly to the cognitive social and emotional development of learners. More over folklore engages children in an enjoyable manner, helping understand and internalize moral and cultural values such as respect for elders, unity, and empathy. This strongly suggests positive acceptance of folklore as a pedagogical resource.

Objective 4: To find out the extent to which folklore is used in classroom teaching practices.

Research question: To what extent do teachers use folktales and folksongs in classroom teachings?

Table 4: Use of folklore in classroom in teaching and learning

Response	Frequency	Percentage
----------	-----------	------------

Yes	25	66.7%
No	05	33.3%
Total	30	100%

Although most teachers believe in the effectiveness of using folklore in teaching cultural values to students, only 66.7% have actually used folklore in teaching, showing a gap in belief and practice. The reasons for not using folklore in classrooms were lack of time and burden of completing the syllabus on time.

Objective 5: To identify the subjects in which folklore can be effectively integrated.

Research question: In which subjects can folklore be effectively integrated?

Table 5: Subjects where folklore fits best into

Subjects	Frequency	Percentage
Language	26	86.7%
Social Science	18	60.0%
Others	04	13.3%

“Note: Multiple responses were allowed; therefore, total frequency exceeds the number of respondents (N=30). Percentages are calculated based on the total number of respondents”

The majority of teachers (86.7%) reported that folklore fits best in Language subjects, followed by Social Science (60%). This indicates that folklore is largely viewed as a literary resource, though its cultural and historical relevance also makes it suitable for Social Science teaching.

Objective 6: To examine teachers’ perception regarding inclusion of folklore in the school curriculum.

Research question: Do teachers’ support the inclusion of folklore in the school curriculum?

Table 6: Folklore inclusion in the school curriculum

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	29	93.3%
No	01	06.7%
Total	30	100%

The findings reveal that 93.3% of the respondents favor the inclusion of folklore in the school curriculum. This indicates a strong positive attitude among teachers towards integrating traditional narratives into formal education.

Objective 7: To examine the methods of integrating folktales and folksongs into education.

Research question: How can folklore and folksongs be incorporated into education?

Table 7: Methods of integrated folklore into teaching value education

Themes Identified	Frequency	Percentage
Story Telling	29	93.3%
Group Discussion	29	93.3%
Role Play	30	100%
Singing	30	100%
Drama	30	100%

“Note: Multiple responses were allowed; therefore, total frequency exceeds the number of respondents (N=30). Percentages are calculated based on the total number of respondents”

The data indicate that teachers strongly support activity-based methods such as role play, singing, and drama (100%) for integrating folklore into teaching. Storytelling and group discussion were also widely recommended (93.3%). This reflects a preference for interactive and experiential learning strategies.

Objective 8: To analyze the perceived benefits of using folklore as pedagogical tool in classroom.

Research question: What benefits do teachers perceive in using folklore in classroom teaching?

Table 8: Benefits of using folklore in classroom teaching

Themes identified	Frequency	Percentage
Better understanding	29	93.3%
Creativity	24	80%
Cultural connection	30	100%
Promotes moral and ethical learning	30	100%

“Note: Multiple responses were allowed; therefore, total frequency exceeds the number of respondents (N=30). Percentages are calculated based on the total number of respondents”

The findings indicate that teachers perceive folklore as a valuable educational resource. All respondents (100%) identified cultural connection and moral and ethical learning as major benefits of incorporating folklore in teaching. A significant majority (93.3%) reported that folklore enhances students’ understanding of concepts, while 80% emphasizes its role in promoting creativity. In addition to the major themes identified, some teachers noted that folklore boosts imagination, preserves local culture, and sparks creativity among learners. These responses highlight the multidimensional impact of folklore, extending beyond moral instruction to cognitive and cultural development.

Objective 9: To identify the challenges faced by teachers in using folklore as a pedagogical tool in the classroom.

Research Question: What challenges do teachers face when using folklore as a teaching tool?

Table 9: Challenges faced by teachers when using folklore for teaching

Themes identified	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of time	30	100%
Lack of sufficient resource	29	93.3%
Curriculum Pressure	30	100%
Language barrier	26	86.7%

“Note: Multiple responses were allowed; therefore, total frequency exceeds the number of respondents (N=30). Percentages are calculated based on the total number of respondents”

All teachers (100%) revealed lack of time and curriculum pressure as major challenges in using folklore for teaching. This indicates that time constraints and syllabus demands are most significant barriers. A high percentage (93.3 %) of teachers also revealed lack of sufficient resource/ documentation, showing that limited teaching materials is another serious concern. Additionally, 86.7% teachers revealed language barriers as a challenge, suggesting that difference in language or students’ proficiency levels may affect the effective use of folklore in classrooms.

Teachers strongly supported the inclusion of local folklore in the school curriculum. All respondents expressed that folklore makes learning meaningful and culturally relevant. They emphasized that folklore helps students understand their traditions, values, and social norms while fostering respect for cultural heritage. Several teachers also noted that folklore enhances socialization skills and connects classroom learning to real life experience, making education more engaging and value-oriented.

Although teachers showed a positive attitude towards using folklore as a teaching tool, some indicated that they would benefit from professional training, workshops, and access to structured instructional materials. While a few teachers felt confident in using folklore independently, many highlighted the need for curriculum support and ready-made teaching resources to implement it more effectively. This suggests that institutional support and professional development opportunities are essential for strengthening classroom integration. Overall, the responses indicate that teachers perceive folklore as a powerful tool for cultural preservation and identity formation.

Conclusion

The present study highlights folklore as a significant pedagogical resource for value education in schools. The findings reveal a strong consensus among teachers regarding the educational and cultural importance of local folktales and folksongs. A majority of teachers are familiar with

local folklore and unanimously agree that it is an effective tool for teaching moral and ethical values. Core values such as respect, hard work, cooperation, kindness, resilience, honesty and unity were consistently identified as key themes embedded in folklore. The study further indicates that folklore is most suitable for integration into Language and Social Science subjects, where storytelling, role play, singing, drama, and group discussions can be effectively employed. Teachers perceive multiple benefits of using folklore in classrooms, including enhanced understanding, creativity, cultural connection, and moral development. These findings affirm that folklore contribute not only to character building but also to cognitive and cultural enrichment

However, despite positive attitudes, challenges such as lack of time, curriculum pressure, insufficient teaching resources, and language barriers hinder its effective implementation. This gap between belief and practice suggests the need for institutional support, curriculum integration, professional training, and development of structured instructional materials.

Overall, the study concludes that integrating folklore into formal education can make learning more meaningful, culturally relevant, and value-oriented. Strengthening support systems for teachers will ensure that folklore continues to serve as a powerful medium for preserving cultural heritage while fostering moral and holistic development among students. In today's fast-paced and AI-driven world, such culturally rooted mediums are increasingly essential to strengthen and inculcate moral values, ensuring that education remains humane, value-oriented, and socially responsible.

Appendix A: Selected Folksongs

Title 1: Gunthe Thombo Ne Kale (from this song we learn to praise God, to be grateful and thankful in one's life)

Title 2: Tsongpon Norbu Zangpo Logdi Mangpo Magai Chiksum Sungho (through this song we learn how hard work, dedication and consistency brings success)

Title 3: Tai Fafdu Tashiwa Sho, Shar Cho tah Shergey Chosa Tashi Sho,woyanga chawa sho (this song takes us through the agricultural fields and sung after sowing barley seed(nai). The song brings the people together, working together, teaching cooperation, sharing ideas, happiness and praying for good harvest.

Appendix B: Selected Folktales

Title 1: Jham-Nynchey Phama (The Kindness of Parents) (Zopa, 2025, p.57)

Title 2: Mee ning Mruuk tam (The tale of the man and the Serpents) (Zopa, 2025, p.70)

Title 3: Rang Shi Chen Matshan (A Selfish Family) (Zopa, 2025, p.78)

Title 4: Mee Shoo (The rich man) (Zopa, 2025, p.92)

Title 5: Puna Blik Tam (The four harmonious friends) (Zopa, 2025, p.9)

Acknowledgement

The author expresses sincere gratitude to all the teachers who participated in this study and shared their valuable insights and experiences. The author also extends heartfelt thanks to the respected community elders and traditional knowledge bearers, particularly Mrs. Sangey Chotton, and Mr. Sangey Dakpa who generously shared traditional folk songs and oral narratives that form an important part of this research. I further extend my gratitude to all my colleagues and the institution for all the support and encouragement during the course of this research.

References

1. Barli, J.,Widyastuti, M., Surtikanti, S., & Sueena, A. S.(2024). *The utilization of local folklore as teaching material: Students' viewpoint and character education. Journal of English Educational Study (JEES)*, 7(1), 82–91.
2. Dundes, A. (1980). *Interpreting folklore*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
3. Farhin, N., & Pratama, G. C. (2025). *Analyzing the Rawa Pening folktale to foster character education in elementary schools: A literature review. International Journal of Active Learning*, 10(2). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.15294/ijal.v10i2.25252>
4. Kusuma, D., & Nurzaman, B. (2024). *The role of folk tales in the formation of children's character: A literature and psychology analysis. Jurnal Jembatan Efektivitas Ilmu dan Akhlak Ahlussunah Wal Jama'ah*, 5(2). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.52188/jeas.v5i2.847>
5. Nanda, D. D., Simbolon, B., Damanik, F. A., & Sembiring, Y. B. (2021). *Moral value and character building education in folklore from Central Java "Timun Mas". Journal of*

- Languages and Language Teaching*, 9(1), 85–91. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.33394/joltt.v9i1.3319>
6. Narayan, K. (1993). *Refractions of India? Genre, ideology, and the study of folklore*. *Cultural Anthropology*, 8(2), 177-203.
 7. Nata, J., & Sembiring, Y.B.(2020). *Moral value and character building education in folklore of Batu Gantung*. *Jurnal iimiah Wahana Pendidikan*, 6(4), 602-601. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4297810>
 8. Rohmat. J. (2023). *The role of folklore in building character and early childhood language skills*. *Child Kingdom: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 2(2), 130-145. Retrieved from <http://doi.org/10.53961/childom.v2i2.190>
 9. Sipahutar , R. A., Sianturi, R.W., & Sembiring, Y. B. (2021). *The value and character building education in folklore from Bataknese "Sigale-Gale"*. *Journal of Language Teaching*, 9(1), 111-116. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.33394/joltt.v9i1.3228>
 10. UNESCO. (2003). *Convention for the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage*. Paris: UNESCO.
 11. Zopa, Y. (2025). *Kitsum Duksum: A compilation of Monpa folk-tales*. Elora Offset.